

GENERALISED ESTIMATION OF YOUNG'S MODULUS OF IRON BY AN EXPANSION INTO DIRECTION COSINES $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ WITH RESPECT TO THE CRYSTAL AXES

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Abstract

In this present article, Young's Modulus is expressed by an expansion into Direction Cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ with respect to the crystal axes. The General Equation of Young's Modulus can be used to determine Y values at $\langle 100 \rangle, \langle 110 \rangle, \langle 111 \rangle$ directions respectively. In the present article Iron, Copper, Aluminum Young's Modulus is determined at $\langle 100 \rangle, \langle 110 \rangle, \langle 111 \rangle$ directions respectively. The Equation can be generalized to include any element with anisotropic property.

Keywords: isotropic, Young's Modulus, Direction Cosines

I. Introduction

Anisotropic Properties are those properties which vary with crystal direction Young's Modulus of iron is different at $\langle 100 \rangle, \langle 110 \rangle, \langle 111 \rangle$ directions viz. 125, 210.5, 272.5 GPa respectively. Young's Modulus can be expressed as an expansion into direction cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ with respect to the crystal axes. In the present article, consideration is made up to three terms.

1.1 Standard Equation:

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

Considered Equation:

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

[uvw]	a	b	c	α_1	α_2	α_3	Y
$\langle 100 \rangle$	0	90°	90°	1	0	0	K_0
$\langle 110 \rangle$	45°	45°	90°	$1/\sqrt{2}$	$1/\sqrt{2}$	0	$K_0 + K_1/4$
$\langle 111 \rangle$	54.7°	54.7°	54.7°	$1/\sqrt{3}$	$1/\sqrt{3}$	$1/\sqrt{3}$	$K_0 + K_1/3 + K_2/27$

II. Calculation Of Young's Modulus For Iron By An Expansion Into Direction Cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ With Respect To The Crystal Axes

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

For <100> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1, \alpha_2 = 0, \alpha_3 = 0 \dots$ [I]

For <110> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_3 = 0 \dots$ [II]

For <111> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{3}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{3}, \alpha_3 = 1/\sqrt{3} \dots$ [III]

2.1 Calculation Of Young's Modulus For Iron By An Expansion Into Direction Cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ With Respect To The Crystal Axes

From Ref ⁵ , We have

Metal	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)		
	[100]	[110]	[111]
Iron	125.0	210.5	272.7

For <100> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1, \alpha_2 = 0, \alpha_3 = 0 \dots$ [I], in Standard Equation

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

We have

$$Y^*_{[100]} = K_0 = 125;$$

For <110> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_3 = 0$

Using [II] , in Standard Equation

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1)$$

$$210.5 = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

$$\Rightarrow 210.5 = 125 + K_1/4 + K_3/16 + K_5/64$$

$$\Rightarrow [16K_1 + 4K_3 + K_5] = 5472 \dots\dots\dots [IV];$$

For <111> directions, $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{3}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{3}, \alpha_3 = 1/\sqrt{3} \dots$ [III];

Using [III] , in Standard Equation

$$Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$$

$$272.7 = 125 + K_1/3 + K_2/27 + K_3/9 + K_4/81 + K_5 /27 + K_6 /729 = 125 + K_1/3 + K_5/27 + K_3/9 + K_4/81 + K_2 /27 + K_6 /729 \text{ [re-arraging } K_2, K_5$$

$$\Rightarrow 27[9K_1 + 3K_3 + K_5] + 9[K_4 + 3K_2 + K_6] = 147.7 * 729 = 107673.3$$

$$\Rightarrow 27 * 3980 + 9 * 23.7 = 107673.3$$

$$\Rightarrow [9K_1 + 3K_3 + K_5] = 3980 \dots [V];$$

$$\Rightarrow [K_4 + 3K_2 + K_6] = 23.7$$

$$\Rightarrow 3 + 6*3 + 2.7 = 23.7$$

$$\Rightarrow K_4 = 3; K_2 = 6; K_6 = 2.7$$

\Rightarrow From [IV] - [V]; We have

$$\Rightarrow 16K_1 + 4K_3 + K_5 = 5472$$

(-)

$$9K_1 + 3K_3 + K_5 = 3980$$

$$7K_1 + K_3 = 1492$$

$$\Rightarrow 7*210 + 22 = 1492;$$

$$\Rightarrow K_1 = 210; K_3 = 22;$$

$$\Rightarrow K_5 = 3980 - 3*22 - 9*210$$

$$\Rightarrow K_5 = 2024$$

Substituting , $K_0, K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4, K_5, K_6$,in standard equation, we have $Y^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_5 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2$

$$K_0 = 125, K_1 = 210, K_2 = 6; K_3 = 22; K_4 = 3; K_5 = 2024; K_6 = 2.7$$

$$Y^*_{\text{IRON}} = 125 + 210 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + 6 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + 22 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + 3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) + 2024 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^3 + 2.7 (\prod \alpha^2_1)^2 \dots \dots \dots [VI];$$

\Rightarrow [VI] ABOVE IS GENERALISED ESTIMATION OF YOUNG'S MODULUS OF IRON BY AN EXPANSION INTO DIRECTION COSINES $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ WITH RESPECT TO THE CRYSTAL AXES

⇒ FOR <100> Directions, $Y^*_{\text{IRON}} = 125$

⇒ FOR <110> Directions, $Y^*_{\text{IRON}} = 125 + 210/4 + 22/16 + 2024/64 = 210.5$

⇒ FOR <111> Directions, $Y^*_{\text{IRON}} = 125 + 210/3 + 6/27 + 22/9 + 3/81 + 2024/27 + 2.7/729 = 272.7$

<i>Metal</i>	<i>Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)</i>		
	<i>[100]</i>	<i>[110]</i>	<i>[111]</i>
Iron	125.0	210.5	272.7

⇒ ABOVE VALUES, CONFORM TO THE STANDARD YOUNG'S MODULUS OF IRON.

III Conclusion.

Young's Modulus of an element can be expressed by an expansion into Direction Cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ with respect to the crystal axes. Generalized equation of Young's Modulus can be utilized to obtain its value at any crystallographic direction with the provision of directional cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ along that particular crystallographic direction.

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